

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**STRATEGIC PLANNING TO SUSTAINABLE RURAL
DEVELOPMENT**¹Edem Kalafatov¹V.I. Vernadsky Crimean Federal University, Simferopol, Russia.**Article Received:** January 2019**Accepted:** February 2019**Published:** March 2019**Abstract:**

Rural areas of the Republic of Crimea, remote from the coastal strip and deprived of the opportunity to attract financial resources through tourism services, are in a crisis economic state, caused by the low level of state attention to the problems of the region. On the basis of the theoretical analysis on the development of rural areas, the main ways of improving the approaches and mechanisms of the socio-economic development of the rural territory of the Republic of Crimea are highlighted. Software products are designed for a medium-term period and are based on previous experience of implementation in the regions of the Russian Federation since 2006. Strategic documents are multi-level in nature and focused on the integrated development of territories in the context of industries, specific objects and areas. Justification of the organizational and methodological situation on the formation of a new tool for the effective development of rural areas, representing a synthesis of various areas of state support, including both traditional strategic and important vector and innovative aspects, is applied and timely in the sustainable development of rural areas. This approach will allow building a new format of the socio-economic environment in rural areas, initiating the growth of investment projects and attracting the attention of potential business.

Key words: Republic of Crimea, tourism, service, rural, development.**Corresponding author:****Edem Kalafatov,**

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Please cite this article in press Edem Kalafatov ., *Strategic Planning To Sustainable Rural Development.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(03).

INTRODUCTION:

Rural areas of the Republic of Crimea, remote from the coastal strip and deprived of the opportunity to attract financial resources through tourism services, are in a crisis economic state, caused by the low level of state attention to the problems of the region. On the basis of the theoretical analysis on the development of rural areas [1, 2], we highlight the main ways to improve the approaches and mechanisms for the socio-economic development of the rural territory of the Republic of Crimea:

- 1- Implementation of targeted state development policy with the help of a set of programs, projects, action plans. Financing in this case is carried out at the expense of the federal budget;
- 2- Activation of the regional business environment, attraction of private investments. In this case, rural territories do not receive adequate funding due to their low attractiveness for investments.
- 3- Symbiosis of events in the form of public-private partnership.

A substantial amount of state programs has been operating in the Republic of Crimea since 2015. A review of implemented software tools to support rural areas in the Republic of Crimea showed that at the moment they are implementing:

- FTP "Socio-economic development of the Republic of Crimea and the city of Sevastopol until 2020";
- SE "Development of agriculture and regulation of the markets of agricultural products, raw materials and food of the Republic of Crimea for 2015-2020";
- SE "Development of resorts and tourism in the Republic of Crimea for 2017-2020";
- The subprogram "Sustainable development of rural areas." The review describes the state programs in the context of the following areas: responsible agencies, developers; terms and stages of implementation; summary of events; degree of influence on processes in rural areas.

Software products are designed for a medium-term period and are based on previous experience of implementation in the regions of the Russian Federation since 2006. Strategic documents are multi-level in nature and focused on the integrated development of territories in the context of industries, specific objects and areas.

All the above programs were developed taking into account the general development policy of the Republic of Crimea as part of the Russian Federation, indicated in the Strategy of Social and Economic Development of the Republic of Crimea until 2030 (Law of the Republic of Crimea December 28, 2016). The document presents an analytical review, justifies

alternative scenarios for the development of the territory, taking into account sanctions restrictions in the economic sphere on the part of foreign policy partners. Special attention is paid to the development of the social sphere: there are developments (activities) focused on various age groups of the population.

The directions of stimulation of the tourist complex are connected with the commissioning of modern complex objects, as well as integration formations in the form of clusters. Rural tourism as a separate direction is declared in one municipal area - Pervomaisky, implementation period until 2026.

Other areas of rural development, stated in the Strategy, are support for the agro-industrial complex, utility infrastructure, and the transport and logistics complex. Sectoral programs are an important factor in the development of rural areas. AIC enterprises implement a number of socio-economic functions and accumulate the effect of comprehensive measures to support the village.

The federal target program "Sustainable Development of Rural Territories" has been implemented on the territory of the Republic of Crimea since 2015, the main directions are:

- solving the housing problem for young families and specialists;
- arrangement of settlements with objects of social and engineering infrastructure;
- Grant support to local initiatives of citizens living in rural areas.

In the analysis of programs affecting the problems of rural areas, implemented in the Republic of Crimea, the following "thin spots" should be noted:

1. Overload of programs with tasks and directions. The principle of complexity in this format loses its economic meaning, due to the low implementation efficiency. Sectoral programs include various areas from infrastructure facilities to social issues.
2. A large number of those responsible and executors, in this situation it is difficult to organize control over the timing, quality and results of the implementation of targeted programs.
3. Lack of interconnection and consistency in the design and implementation of programs. The programs are made earlier than the basic strategy for the development of the regional socio-economic environment.
4. The inability to revise tasks and redirect funding to other projects, in view of changing conditions. In the process of implementing approved and approved projects, there is no adaptive mechanism for changing

target control points of measures, which reduces the final effectiveness of projects.

5. Government programs are implemented on the territory of the Republic of Crimea during the implementation of the legislative framework to the conditions of operation within the Russian Federation and do not provide for the lack of experience in the use of complex program projects taking into account the mentality of the local population.

6. Support for rural areas is carried out in the areas listed in a number of documents, with the deadlines, performers and responsible actors are different and do not have an interrelated plan.

Thus, there is no software product that considers rural areas as a central object of stimulation. The focus at the regional and municipal levels does not allow an objective assessment of the need of rural areas for additional measures and areas of support. The development of the rural socio-economic system takes place through the point of complex work in the traditional and innovative areas. However, the rural environment, integrated into the regional economic system, is the least stable space in terms of the escalation of innovations. An extensive layer of planned areas for stimulating development is associated with innovative tools: technology parks, alternative energy, logistics, integration education, and so on. For rural areas, "soft innovations" or the gradual implementation of innovations are appropriate.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Considering the rural areas from the standpoint of demographic content, it should be noted the strengthening of the aging of the village and active migration to the urban environment. For these reasons, it is important to massively popularize rural life, modernize the infrastructure of rural areas, taking into account the actual needs and readiness of the local population to actively operate the facilities.

For the formation of a target program to stimulate the development of rural areas based on the problem-stopping approach, we consider it expedient to single out the areas of support in the priority order: social development; economic development; rural tourism development; investment attractiveness; infrastructure development.

As part of the above areas, we have identified a new - rural tourism. Rural tourism can be described as the movement and temporary residence of the population (mainly urban) in rural areas, coupled with the redistribution of funds from the urban environment to the rural. This implies the availability of the necessary infrastructure in rural areas to maintain a

certain level of comfort.

Stimulating rural tourism as a new type of economic activity for the study area is a resource-intensive, but promising direction. Developing the strategic directions of socio-economic nature, a base is being formed for the implementation of rural tourism. Increasing the attractiveness of rural areas is a priority for the tourism business, which in search of new ideas and unusual forms of recreation uses their resource base.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

At the time of the study, there is a serious layer of problems in rural areas that do not allow competing with traditional tourist services:

- lack of infrastructural security of the territories to create comfortable rest conditions;
- low degree of implementation of tourism services in rural areas;
- lack of qualified personnel in rural areas;
- undeveloped tourist niche in rural areas due to the low standard of living of the local population;
- low level of entrepreneurial activity, social passivity of the population.

To solve the problems posed, a step-by-step guide on the implementation of program activities in rural conditions is necessary. The first stage is a set of preliminary procedures necessary to determine the feasibility of the formation of measures of support and development. It includes activities to review the general trends of the territory, the critical assessment of the positive and negative effects of projects implemented on the current date.

Separately, it is necessary to substantiate the applicability of scientific approaches to the formation of programs: rational; system; institutional; comparative (comparative); integration; dynamic; directive; optimization.

The use of this set of approaches will reduce the risks at subsequent stages of implementation.

Elements of the mechanism for the implementation of policy documents on sustainable rural development:

- organizational component - the register of responsible executors and controlling entities;
- financial component - identification of the main sources of financing and methods of their distribution.

Instruments for the implementation of state program projects:

- organizational and structural (innovative enterprises, technology parks, clusters, integration education);
- financial (various types of investment by source and form, equity);

- material and technical (leasing, cooperatives, collective ownership);
- personnel;
- institutional (tax system, legislative and regulatory framework, informal norms and rules).

At the preliminary stage, the key point is the coordination of the structure and components of the program for stimulating the development of rural territories; in this connection, the author introduces the concept of a "hybrid target program". This type of program is a set of measures for the development of problem areas - rural areas, with the incorporation of individual areas included in previously implemented government projects, but not targeted at the village level (previously, these measures included implementation at the level of municipal districts in general).

The second stage - the implementation stage - contains an active procedure for implementing the directions of incentive programs. In the conditions of the Republic of Crimea, it is necessary to apply the method of pilot implementation of selective provisions on the example of individual territories. The results of the implementation of program documents are evaluated by comparing target indicators with planning data. The essential difference between the proposed model for the implementation of programs is the inclusion of an adjustment point that allows combining and reorienting financing, taking into account the prevailing economic conditions. After this process, a comprehensive implementation of the state program

throughout the territory of the Republic of Crimea is possible.

An important link in the implementation of programs is their support in the form of information support and monitoring. Consulting support is a prerequisite for the effective work of program participants, smoothes the level of risk of misuse of financial resources, and also helps to maintain the active interaction of all involved actors.

The implementation phase is indicative and on the database obtained as a result of its execution, a decision is made to extend the implementation deadlines and expand the territorial areas of software implementation.

The reporting mechanism is formed through the timely preparation of declarative forms, reflecting the real results of activities.

The third stage is post-sales. It is an analytical procedure, which includes a number of sub-steps:

1. interpretation of individual reports in various areas of support;
2. calculation of the effectiveness of program implementation across the support subjects;
3. calculation of the effectiveness of the implementation of the program in rural entities;
4. change (growth / decline) of targets in rural areas;
5. Changes in targets across the region.

Imagine the author's approach to the formation of targeted programs for the development of rural areas (Table 1).

Table 1: Directions for design the targeted programs to stimulate the rural areas development

Directions of support	Expected results
1. Social development of rural areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Smoothing inertia processes in rural areas; - Improving the level of comfort of the rural population; - Growth of demographic indicators; - Cultural development of the territory; - Reducing ethnic tensions; - General reduction of social tension in rural areas; - Social security of rural areas; - Reduced criminality in rural areas; - Accessibility of social assistance to socially unprotected groups of the population; - Preservation of cultural heritage and identity of rural areas.

2. Economic development of rural areas	Direct effects: - Formation of the entrepreneurial business community; - Filling budgets; - Employment; - Creating a competitive environment in rural areas; - Close cooperation of business and government; - Increasing the level of trust in the government; - High margin business; - Formation of a network of local economies; Indirect effects: - Social effect (additional jobs; the need to improve skills and others); - Growth of rating characteristics of rural areas
3. Development of rural tourism	- The possibility of paired business activities for the rural population; - Growing interest in the village, as a territory for living and livelihoods; - Involvement of new territories in the tourist segment; -Extra rural income.
4. Investment attractiveness of rural areas	- Entry into the market of investment projects; - Ability to transform the scale of the business; - Promotion of entrepreneurial activity.
5. Infrastructure development of rural areas	- Improving the quality of life of the population; - Increased availability of socio-economic benefits for the rural population; - Reducing inter-territorial disparities between urban and rural infrastructure.

We have identified five strategic areas of support, some of them are traditional and at the time of the study are actively implemented within the framework of state targeted programs, some areas are original and in an expanded format are not implemented in the territory of the Republic of Crimea. Consider them in more detail.

The development of rural tourism. This type of economic activity is in a “rudimentary” state and does not have sufficient experience of successful functioning in the study area. It is possible to predict various scenarios for the development of this tourism service in the Republic of Crimea, taking into account the growing flow of tourists to the region and the need to maximize the list of tourist destinations and satisfy all the tourist needs of the population arriving in the region.

The formation and development of rural tourism can be described by the following scenarios [4]:

- 1 script. Formation of a competitive tourist service at the expense of own funds of local entrepreneurs.
- 2 script. The development of the necessary conditions and facilities for the formation of a rural tourism system through the targeted implementation of state programs and the infusion of budgetary funds.
- 3 script. Formation of the necessary infrastructure of the region to attract third-party financial resources in the form of domestic and foreign investments.
- 4 script. Synchronous development of village-

forming branches of agriculture and rural tourism.

In the Russian context of the socio-economic decline of rural areas and a steady outflow of population, the development of rural tourism is necessary to solve many tasks, besides the traditionally low standard of living, lack of jobs, destruction of the social infrastructure; heritage and other intangible values.

Rural tourism contributes to the formation of a healthy living environment for the local population and to attract the attention of the tourist flow.

Investment attractiveness of rural areas. Innovative this direction is due to the specific addressee of investment injections. Rural areas are rarely invested as an independent business project. The low level of competitiveness of entrepreneurial initiatives in rural areas is due to a low level of demand, or a steady disregard for any innovations in the rural environment.

According to the Ministry of Economic Development of the Republic of Crimea, the following investment projects are being implemented within rural areas [5]:

1. The development of winemaking in the village Koktebel - 1,408,000 thousand rubles;
2. The development of viticulture in the area with Landslide - 2968.04 thousand rubles;
3. Organization of growing grain and leguminous crops in the Dzhankoy region of the Republic of Crimea - 28,257.3 thousand rubles;

4. Development of KFH "OFK" - 100 000.00 thousand rubles;
5. Creating a profitable agricultural complex in the field of crop production for growing grassy cereals and industrial crops - 6,819.68 thousand rubles;
6. Creation of a wine-making enterprise on the basis of the state enterprise "State Farm-Zavetnoe" state enterprise - 594,482.2 thousand rubles;
7. Construction of a sheep farm for 2000 heads in s. Red - 22,830.0 thousand rubles;
8. Growing grains, legumes and oilseeds; stocking feed for livestock and domestic sales - 74,243.70 thousand rubles;
9. Reconstruction and development of the poultry factory for the production of poultry meat and chicken eggs - 3172020 thousand rubles;
10. Laying out a garden on 120 hectares (p. Privetnoye) - 6,09087.14 thousand rubles;
11. Cultivation of table grapes in the Saksy district - 62400 thousand rubles;
12. Creation of a modern agricultural enterprise with a closed production cycle (Belogorsk district) - 590042 thousand rubles;
13. Organization of coastal fishing in order to ensure year-round supply of fish products to the consumer market (Olenevo rural settlement) - 8,000 thousand rubles;
14. Organization of fishery (Olenevskoe rural settlement) - 8,000 thousand rubles. and so forth. Total 20 programs.

There is also a separate number of infrastructure projects initiated as part of state programs for the socio-economic development of the region. In this regard, it is obvious that the main investment and competitive sector within the borders of rural areas is the agro-industrial complex, this is due to the natural and climatic conditions of the region and the growth of food security.

The purpose of the hybrid incentive program for rural areas is the development of alternative and related areas of investment (for example, rural tourism), which will attract the resident population to rural areas and realize the entrepreneurial potential of the creative group of the population.

CONCLUSION:

Thus, the substantiation of the position of the organizational and methodological nature of the formation of a new tool for the effective development of rural areas - strategic programs, which are a synthesis of various areas of state support, including both traditional strategic vector and innovative aspects, is applied and timely in the sustainable development of rural areas. territories.

The effects of the implementation of such programs

will be in the state participation in those areas of the socio-economic life of rural areas that have not been covered by the program-targeted activities. This approach will allow building a new format of the socio-economic environment in rural areas, initiating the growth of investment projects and attracting the attention of potential business.

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